

Efficacy of Thrombopoietin Receptor Agonists for the Treatment of a Patient with Immune Thrombocytopenia after CAR T-cell Therapy for Multirefractory Primary Mediastinal Large B-cell Lymphoma

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ABSTRACT

Chimeric antigen receptor T (CART) cell therapy has made its way over the years, representing an effective evolution of chemo-free treatments for numerous hematological malignancies and beyond, due to their powerful efficacy against tumor cells.

We describe the clinical case of a young woman with multirefractory aggressive Primary Mediastinal Large B-cell Lymphoma (PMBCL) who developed Immune Thrombocytopenia (ITP) after more than a year from CAR T-cells treatment. All investigations of differential diagnostics of thrombocytopenia were carried out, including bone marrow biopsy, and the diagnosis of primary ITP was confirmed. We extensively discussed on the likely causes of ITP, such as various treatments practiced by the patient (7 lines of chemo-immunotherapy), including anti-CD30 brentuximab and anti-PD1 nivolumab, as a bridge to CAR T-cells. Our case seems to be the only reported in the world, as the other two reports were described in patients with multiple myeloma, so we want to share the effectiveness and safety of treatment with TPO-RA, as known for the primary forms of ITP.

INTRODUCTION

Chimeric Antigen Receptor T (CART) cell therapy represents an innovative treatment for patients with numerous relapsed or refractory hematological malignancies [1]. It often causes hematologic toxicity, including thrombocytopenia, more and more often managed with thrombopoietin receptor agonists (TPO-RAs) [2]. Romiplostim and Eltrombopag before, Avatrombopagin recent years are the three TPO-RAs used worldwide for the

treatment of relapsed/refractory Immune Thrombocytopenia (ITP) after conventional first-line therapies with steroids \pm immunoglobulins \pm immunosuppressors [3]. The response rate of these drugs exceeds 80% to 90%, thus revolutionizing the prognosis of patients with ITP and always being used in the treatment of other forms of thrombocytopenia, such as those of a plastic anemias or post-transplant aplasia, complicated by very nuanced side effects and very slight increase in thrombotic risk in patients without predisposing factors [4].

Regarding CART-cells treatment, the most known and frequent side effects include Cytokine Release Syndrome (CRS) and Immune Effectors Cell-Associated Neurotoxicity Syndrome (ICANS), but not rare early hematological toxicity caused by them is, even prolonged [5,6]. Thus, over the last few months the role of TPO-RAs has also been extended to the treatment of these forms of thrombocytopenia, whose pathogenesis does not always appear clear [2]. Our case concerns a patient who developed late ITP after treatment with CAR T-cell for multirefractory aggressive Primary Mediastinal Large B-cell Lymphoma (PMBCL) that, looking at the literature, seems to be the only reported in the world, as the other two reports were described in four patients with multiple myeloma [7,8].

CASE REPORT

We describe the case of a 44-year-old woman diagnosed in June 2018 with Primary Mediastinal large B-cell Lymphoma (PMBCL) and treated with seven lines of chemo-immunotherapy treatment, including autologous stem cell transplantation and, at last, immune checkpoint inhibitor nivolumab in combination with anti-CD30 Brentuximab off label as bridge to CAR T-cell therapy. In July 2021 she was treated with axicabtageneclisoleucel, obtaining a complete remission with full hematological recovery within 3 months (Figure 1). Bone marrow biopsy confirmed absence of signs of dysplasia and patient began follow up. In May 2022, ten months after CAR T-cell therapy, she went to the emergency room for metrorrhagia, and bruising spread due to severe thrombocytopenia (platelets 2.000/mm³), without additional alterations of the blood count. She practiced treatment with high dose steroids and intravenous immunoglobulins, obtaining a poor response. So, a marrow aspiration was done confirming the diagnosis of Immune Thrombocytopenia (ITP). Therefore, we decided to start early treatment with the oral Thrombopoietin Receptor Agonist (TPO-RA) Eltrombopag, quickly reaching the full dose of 75 mg once a day, achieving a complete but short-lived response. Thus, for PLT 6.000/mm³, she was switched with subcutaneous TPO-RA Romiplostim at the starting dose of 3 mcg/kg/week.

Figure 1: Positron Emission Tomography after CAR T-cell therapy.

After only one administration of Romiplostim, the patient showed rapid response, with the development of thrombocytosis after the second administration and subsequent temporary discontinuation for 3 weeks. Then the treatment was resumed at the minimum dose of 1 mcg/kg/week, which the patient continues until today without complications and maintaining a platelet count constantly higher than 100,000/mm³, compatible with a complete response, that meet the criteria for starting taper in order to pursue a free-treatment remission (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Platelet trends during treatment with TPO-RAs for ITP.

DISCUSSION

Our report aims to share our experience with a category of less frequent side effects with new treatments, such as CAR T-cells. Although the immuno-mediated pathogenesis of the thrombocytopenia of our patient was clear, we are not sure what the most accused treatment may be. In fact, anti-PD1 drugs are also known to cause immune cytopenia⁹, and our patient had received nivolumab immediately before cellular therapy as a bridge. However, these complications are expected within 3 months - 6 months of these treatments, while our patient has developed ITP after more than a year¹⁰. Thus, the pathogenetic mechanism that we think most likely is a secondary complication of immunological disreactivity, due to the combination of lymphoma and treatments received, without being able to exclude late CAR T-cell therapy complication.

CONCLUSION

Dysimmune complications of CAR T-cell therapy may also include immune thrombocytopenia, which responds to therapy with TPO-RAs, like primary forms. They are also used in the management of the early stage of the hematological toxicity of the cellular therapy, showing high efficacy and good safety profile. However, it is important to emphasize the excellent response obtained by the patient to TPO-RA treatment, in the same way as primary ITP forms, thus expanding the potential spectrum of use of these drugs.

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